

ON THE EIGENSTRUCTURES OF BICOMPLEX K-POTENT MATRICES

Jogendra Kumar*¹, Hamant Kumar*²

*¹ Assistant Professor, Mathematics, Govt. Degree College, Raza Nagar, Swar, Rampur, UP, India

*² Assistant Professor, Mathematics, V. A. Govt. Degree College, Atrauli, Aligarh, UP, India

ABSTRACT

In this paper we have studied Bicomplex k -Potent matrices satisfies the equation $A^k = \alpha I + \beta A$, where $A \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$, k is a positive integer, α and β are real numbers. This class of Bicomplex matrices includes Idempotent, Involutory, Nilpotent, Periodic, Skew-periodic, Generalized Involutory, Generalized Skew-Involutory and many more. We have investigated the Eigenstructure of Bicomplex k -Potent matrices and their diagonalizability.

Keywords: Bicomplex Matrix, Idempotent Matrix, Nilpotent Matrix, Involutory Matrix, Periodic Matrix, Skew-Periodic Matrix, Unipotent Matrix, Eigenvalue, Diagonalizable Matrix.

AMS Subject Classification: 30G35, 32A30, 15A18.

I. INTRODUCTION

Yan Wu and Daniel F. Linder [10] studied a class of k -potent complex matrix

$$\{A \in \mathbb{C}_1^{n \times n} : A^k = \alpha I + \beta A, \alpha\beta = 0, \alpha, \beta \in \{-1, 0, 1\}, k \geq 2\}.$$

They called Unipotent matrix which satisfies $A^k = I$, k is a index of A and Skew-unipotent matrix which satisfies $A^k = -I$, k is index of A but the structure of these matrix differ from Unipotent matrix so we renamed such matrix as Generalized involutory and Generalized Skew-involutory matrix. In that sense $A \in \mathbb{C}_1^{n \times n}$ is said to be Generalized Involutory Matrix of index k if $A^k = I$, where k is the least positive integer and Generalized Skew-Involutory matrix of index k if $A^k = -I$, where k is the least positive integer. They show that Periodic, Skew-periodic, Generalized Involutory and Generalized Skew-Involutory Matrices are diagonalizable.

II. Bicomplex Matrix ([1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9])

We denote $\mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n} = \{A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} : \xi_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}_2\}$ the set of $m \times n$ matrices with bicomplex entries.

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n} \Rightarrow \xi_{ij} \in \mathbb{C}_2$

2.1 Idempotent Representation of Bicomplex Matrix

(I) $\mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_1)$ -idempotent representation of Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n}$

$$A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} = [{}^1\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} e_1 + [{}^2\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} e_2 = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2, \text{ where } {}^1A = [{}^1\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n}, {}^2A = [{}^2\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_1)$$

(II) $\mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_2)$ -idempotent representation Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{m \times n}$

$$A = [\xi_{ij}]_{m \times n} = [\xi_{1,ij}]_{m \times n} e_1 + [\xi_{2,ij}]_{m \times n} e_2 = A_1 e_1 + A_2 e_2, \text{ where } A_1 = [\xi_{1,ij}]_{m \times n}, A_2 = [\xi_{2,ij}]_{m \times n} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}(i_2)$$

2.2. Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors of a Bicomplex Matrix

2.2.1 Eigenvalues of a Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}_2$, then the matrix $A - \lambda I$ is called the characteristic matrix of A and $P(\lambda) = \det(A - \lambda I)$ is called characteristic polynomial of A .

The equation $\det(A - \lambda I) = 0$ is called the characteristic equation of A and the roots of this equation are called characteristic roots or latent roots or characteristic values or eigenvalues of the matrix A . The set of all eigenvalues of the matrix A is denoted by $A(\lambda)$.

Note 2.1: $A(\lambda) = {}^1A({}^1\lambda)e_1 + {}^2A({}^2\lambda)e_2$ is the collection of all eigenvalues of A iff ${}^1A({}^1\lambda)$ and ${}^2A({}^2\lambda)$ are spectrum of 1A and 2A respectively.

2.2.2 Eigenvectors of a Bicomplex Matrix

Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}_2$ is an eigenvalue of A , then there exist $X = {}^1X e_1 + {}^2X e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times 1}$, ${}^1X \neq 0$ and ${}^2X \neq 0$ such that $AX = \lambda X$, then X is called characteristic vector or eigenvector of A corresponding to the eigenvalue λ .

Theorem 2.1: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$, ${}^1A, {}^2A \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}(i_1)$. Then A is diagonalizable iff 1A and 2A are diagonalizable.

Bicomplex Nilpotent Matrix 2.1:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex nilpotent matrix of index $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the nilpotent matrices of indices k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be bicomplex nilpotent matrix of index k if 1A and 2A are the nilpotent matrices of index k .

Bicomplex Unipotent Matrix 2.2:

The bicomplex square matrix $U \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be bicomplex unipotent matrix if $U = I + N$, where I is the identity matrix and N is nilpotent.

Bicomplex Periodic Matrix 2.3:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex periodic matrix of period $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the periodic matrix of periods k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex periodic matrix of period k if 1A and 2A are the periodic matrices of period k .

Bicomplex Skew-Periodic Matrix 2.4:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be bicomplex skew-periodic matrix of period $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the skew-periodic matrix of periods k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a bicomplex skew-periodic matrix of period k if 1A and 2A are the skew-periodic matrices of period k .

Generalized Bicomplex Involutionary Matrix 2.5:

The bicomplex square matrix $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be generalized bicomplex involutionary matrix of index $k_1 e_1 + k_2 e_2$ if 1A and 2A are the generalized involutionary matrix of indices k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

In particular $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ is said to be a generalized bicomplex involutionary matrix of index k if 1A and 2A are the generalized involutionary matrix of index k .

Example 2.1:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ ae_1 & 0 & 0 \\ be_1 + de_2 & ce_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a & 0 & 0 \\ b & c & 0 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ a & 0 & 0 \\ b & c & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^2 \neq 0, ({}^1A)^3 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 3$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 2$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a nilpotent matrix of index $3e_1 + 2e_2$.

Example 2.2:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} e_2 & e_1 - e_2 \\ e_2 & -e_2 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^2 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 2.$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = 0 \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a nilpotent matrix of index } 2.$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a nilpotent matrix of index 2.

Example 2.3:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow A^2 = \begin{bmatrix} e_1^2 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 & 0 \\ 0 & e_2 \end{bmatrix} = A$$

$\Rightarrow A$ is idempotent matrix.

Example 2.4:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 e_1 & e_2 \\ -e_2 & -i_1 e_1 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^4 = I \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 4}$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = -I \Rightarrow ({}^2A)^4 = I \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 4}$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a periodic matrix with period 4.

Example 2.5:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 e_1 & i_1 e_2 \\ -i_1 e_2 & -i_1 e_1 \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow {}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, {}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & i_1 \\ -i_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$${}^1A = \begin{bmatrix} i_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i_1 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^1A)^4 = I \Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 4}$$

$${}^2A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & i_1 \\ -i_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, ({}^2A)^2 = I \Rightarrow {}^2A \text{ is a periodic matrix with period 2}$$

Therefore $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a periodic matrix with period $4e_1 + 2e_2$.

III. Class of Bicomplex k – potent Matrices

The class of Bicomplex k – potent Matrix defined as

$$T = \left\{ A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n} : A^k = \alpha I + \beta A, \alpha \beta = 0, \alpha, \beta \in \{-1, 0, 1\}, k \geq 2 \right\}$$

We consider those Bicomplex matrices in the class T that satisfy the following condition

If $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is a bicomplex k – potent Matrix, then both 1A and 2A are k – potent Matrix i.e. k is the smallest positive integer for which $({}^1A)^k = \alpha I + \beta {}^1A$ and $({}^2A)^k = \alpha I + \beta {}^2A$.

Precisely, If k is the index of $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$, so k is the index of both 1A and 2A .

Case(i) For $k = 2, \alpha = 0, \beta = 1, A^2 = A$ i.e. A is a Bicomplex idempotent matrix

Case(ii) For $\alpha = 0, \beta = 1, A^k = A$ i.e. A is a Bicomplex periodic matrix. If k is the index of A , then A is the Bicomplex periodic matrix with period $k - 1$.

Case(iii) For $\alpha = 0, \beta = -1, A^k = -A$ i.e. A is Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrix. If k is the index of A , then A is the Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrix with period $k - 1$.

Case(iv) For $k = k, \alpha = 0, \beta = 0, A^k = O$. If k is the index of A , then A is the Bicomplex Nilpotent Matrix of index k .

Case(v) For $k = 2, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0, A^2 = I$ i.e. A is Bicomplex involutory matrix.

Case(vi) For $k = k, \alpha = 1, \beta = 0, A^k = I$. If k is the index of A , then A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k .

Case(vii) For $k = k, \alpha = -1, \beta = 0, A^k = -I$. If k is the index of A , then A is the Generalized Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrix of index k .

Proposition 3.1:

Let $N \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a nilpotent matrix of index m and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then $\lambda = 0$.

Proof: Let $N \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a nilpotent matrix of index m

Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix N associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow NX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow N(NX) = N(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = \lambda(NX)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = \lambda^2 X$$

$$\Rightarrow N^m X = \lambda^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow 0X = \lambda^m X \quad (\because N^m = 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow 0 = \lambda^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda^m X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^m {}^1X e_1 + {}^2\lambda^m {}^2X e_2 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^m {}^1X = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^m {}^2X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^m = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^m = 0 \quad (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda = 0$$

Proposition 3.2:

Let $N \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a non-zero nilpotent matrix of index m , then N is not diagonalizable.

Proof: Let N is diagonalizable

\Rightarrow There exist an invertible matrix $P \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$

such that $P^{-1}NP = D$

According to proposition 3.1, eigenvalues of N are zero

$$\Rightarrow D = 0$$

$\Rightarrow N = 0$, contradicting that N is non-zero matrix.

Proposition 3.3:

Let $U \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a Unipotent Matrix of index m and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then $\lambda = 1$.

Proof: $U = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a unipotent matrix of index m

$\Rightarrow U = I + N$, where I is the identity matrix and N is nilpotent of index m

Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix U associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow UX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow (I + N)X = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow X + NX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow NX = (\lambda - 1)X$$

$$\Rightarrow N(NX) = (\lambda - 1)NX$$

$$\Rightarrow N^2X = (\lambda - 1)^2X \quad (\because NX = (\lambda - 1)X)$$

$$\Rightarrow N^m X = (\lambda - 1)^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow 0X = (\lambda - 1)^m X \quad (\because N^m = 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow 0 = (\lambda - 1)^m X$$

$$\Rightarrow (\lambda - 1)^m X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - 1)({}^1X) e_1 + ({}^2\lambda - 1)({}^2X) e_2 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - 1)^m = 0 \text{ and } ({}^2\lambda - 1)^m = 0 \quad (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda = 1$$

Proposition 3.4: Let $A \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a periodic matrix of period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 \mid p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow A(AX) = A(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(AX)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda^2 X$$

$$\Rightarrow A^{k+1} X = \lambda^{k+1} X$$

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda^{k+1} X \quad (\because A^{k+1} = A)$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda X = \lambda^{k+1} X$$

$$\Rightarrow (\lambda - \lambda^{k+1}) X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - {}^1\lambda^{k+1}) {}^1 X e_1 + ({}^2\lambda - {}^2\lambda^{k+1}) {}^2 X e_2 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda - {}^1\lambda^{k+1}) {}^1 X = 0 \text{ and } ({}^2\lambda - {}^2\lambda^{k+1}) {}^2 X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda - {}^1\lambda^{k+1} = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda - {}^2\lambda^{k+1} = 0 \quad (\because {}^1 X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2 X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda(1 - {}^1\lambda^k) = 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda(1 - {}^2\lambda^k) = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, (1)^\frac{1}{k} \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, (1)^\frac{1}{k}$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)}; p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)}; q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 \mid p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2p\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2q\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Note 3.1: Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a periodic matrix of period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

(i) A contains $(k+1)^2$ distinct eigenvalues

(ii) $\|\lambda\| \in \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1 \right\}$

Proposition 3.5: Bicomplex periodic matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Bicomplex periodic matrix of period k

$$\Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ and } {}^2A \text{ are periodic matrix of period } k$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1A \text{ and } {}^2A \text{ are diagonalizable}$$

$$\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2 \text{ is diagonalizable}$$

Proposition 3.6:

Let $A \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a Skew-Periodic matrix with period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 \mid p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ \cup \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow A(AX) = A(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(AX)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2 X = \lambda^2 X$$

$$\Rightarrow A^{k+1} X = \lambda^{k+1} X$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow -AX &= \lambda^{k+1}X && (\because A^{k+1} = -A) \\ \Rightarrow -\lambda X &= \lambda^{k+1}X \\ \Rightarrow (-\lambda - \lambda^{k+1})X &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (\lambda + \lambda^{k+1})X &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda + {}^1\lambda^{k+1}){}^1X e_1 + ({}^2\lambda + {}^2\lambda^{k+1}){}^2X e_2 &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow ({}^1\lambda + {}^1\lambda^{k+1}){}^1X &= 0 \text{ and } ({}^2\lambda + {}^2\lambda^{k+1}){}^2X = 0 \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda + {}^1\lambda^{k+1} &= 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda + {}^2\lambda^{k+1} = 0 && (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0) \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda(1 + {}^1\lambda^k) &= 0 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda(1 + {}^2\lambda^k) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} &\text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = 0, e^{i_1(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k})}; p = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 &\text{ and } {}^2\lambda = 0, e^{i_1(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k})}; q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \\ \Rightarrow \lambda \in \{0\} \cup \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k})} e_1 \mid p = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\} &\cup \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \\ &\cup \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k})} e_1 + e^{i_1(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid p, q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Note 3.2: Let $A = [\xi_{ij}]_{n \times n} \in \mathbb{C}_2^{n \times n}$ be a Skew-Periodic matrix with period k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

(i) A contains $(k + 1)^2$ distinct eigenvalues.

(ii) $\|\lambda\| \in \left\{ 0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, 1 \right\}$

Proposition 3.7: Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Bicomplex Skew-periodic matrix of period k

$\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are Skew-periodic matrix of period k

$\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are diagonalizable

$\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is diagonalizable

Proposition 3.8:

Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2p\pi}{k})} e_1 + e^{i_1(\frac{2q\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid p, q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\Rightarrow AX = \lambda X$$

$$\Rightarrow A(AX) = A(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2X = \lambda(AX)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2X = \lambda(\lambda X)$$

$$\Rightarrow A^2X = \lambda^2X$$

$$\Rightarrow A^kX = \lambda^kX$$

$$\Rightarrow IX = \lambda^kX$$

$$(\because A^k = I)$$

$$\Rightarrow X = \lambda^kX$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \lambda^k)X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \lambda^k)X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - {}^1\lambda^k){}^1X e_1 + (1 - {}^2\lambda^k){}^2X e_2 = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - {}^1\lambda^k){}^1X = 0 \text{ and } (1 - {}^2\lambda^k){}^2X = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 - {}^1\lambda^k = 0 \text{ and } 1 - {}^2\lambda^k = 0$$

$$(\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0)$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^k = 1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^k = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = (1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = (1)^{\frac{1}{k}}$$

$$\Rightarrow {}^1\lambda = e^{i_1(\frac{2p\pi}{k})}; p = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = e^{i_1(\frac{2q\pi}{k})}; q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda \in \left\{ e^{i_1(\frac{2p\pi}{k})} e_1 + e^{i_1(\frac{2q\pi}{k})} e_2 \mid p, q = 0,1,2, \dots, k-1 \right\}$$

Note 3.3: Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k and λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

- (i) A contains k^2 distinct eigenvalues
- (ii) $\|\lambda\| = 1$

Proposition 3.9: Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are Generalized involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are diagonalizable
 $\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is diagonalizable

Proposition 3.10:

Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrix of index k and let λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

$$\lambda \in \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\}.$$

Proof: Let X be the eigenvector of the matrix A associated with the eigenvalue λ

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow AX &= \lambda X \\ \Rightarrow A(AX) &= A(\lambda X) \\ \Rightarrow A^2X &= \lambda(AX) \\ \Rightarrow A^2X &= \lambda(\lambda X) \\ \Rightarrow A^2X &= \lambda^2 X \\ \Rightarrow A^k X &= \lambda^k X \\ \Rightarrow -IX &= \lambda^k X && (\because A^k = -I) \\ \Rightarrow -X &= \lambda^k X \\ \Rightarrow (1 + \lambda^k)X &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (1 + {}^1\lambda^k)X e_1 + (1 + {}^2\lambda^k)X e_2 &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (1 + {}^1\lambda^k)X &= 0 \text{ and } (1 + {}^2\lambda^k)X = 0 \\ \Rightarrow 1 + {}^1\lambda^k &= 0 \text{ and } 1 + {}^2\lambda^k = 0 && (\because {}^1X \neq 0 \text{ and } {}^2X \neq 0) \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda^k &= -1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda^k = -1 \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda &= (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = (-1)^{\frac{1}{k}} \\ \Rightarrow {}^1\lambda &= e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)}; p = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \text{ and } {}^2\lambda = e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)}; q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \\ \Rightarrow \lambda &\in \left\{ e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(p+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_1 + e^{i_1 \left(\frac{2(q+1)\pi}{k} \right)} e_2 \mid p, q = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Note 3.4: Let A is the Generalized Bicomplex involutory matrix of index k and λ be an eigenvalue of A , then

- (i) A contains k^2 distinct eigenvalues
- (ii) $\|\lambda\| = 1$

Proposition 3.11: Generalized Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrices are diagonalizable.

Proof: Let $A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ be a Bicomplex Skew-involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are Skew-involutory matrix of index k
 $\Rightarrow {}^1A$ and 2A are diagonalizable
 $\Rightarrow A = {}^1A e_1 + {}^2A e_2$ is diagonalizable

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am heartily thankful to Dr. R.S. Giri, Govt. Degree College, Raza Nagar, Swar, Rampur (UP), Dr. Sukhdev Singh, Lovely Professional University, Punjab and all staff of Govt. Degree College, Raza Nagar, Swar, Rampur (UP) for their encouragement and support during the preparation of this paper.

IV. REFERENCES

- [1] Price, G. B. (1991) "An introduction to multicomplex space and Functions" Marcel Dekker
- [2] Luna-Elizarrarás, M.E., Shapiro, M., Struppa, D. C., Vajiac, A.(2015) "Bicomplex Holomorphic Functions:The Algebra, Geometry and Analysis of Bicomplex Numbers" Springer International Publishing.
- [3] Kumar, J.(2018) "On Some Properties of Bicomplex Numbers •Conjugates •Inverse •Modulii" Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR), .5(9), 475-499
- [4] Srivastava, Rajiv K. (2008) "Certain Topological Aspects of Bicomplex Space". Bull. Pure & Appl. Math, 222-234.
- [5] Alpay, D., Luna-Elizarrarás, M. E., Shapiro, M. , Struppa, D. C. (2014) "Basics of Functional Analysis with Bicomplex Scalars and Bicomplex Schur Analysis" Springer International Publishing, 19-30.
- [6] Kumar, J. (2016) "Conjugation of Bicomplex Matrix" J. of Science and Tech. Res. (JSTR), 1(1), 24-28.
- [7] Kumar, J. (2022) "A Note on Eigenvalues of Bicomplex Matrix" Int. J. of Research Publication and Reviews, 3(10), 771-793.
- [8] Kumar, J. (2022) "Diagonalization of the Bicomplex Matrix" Int. J. of Research Publication and Reviews, 3(11), 105-116.
- [9] Kumar, J. (2022) "On Some Properties of Determinants of Bicomplex Matrices " Journal of Science and Technological Researches (JSTR), 4(3), 20-31.
- [10] Wu, Yan, F. Linder, Daniel (2010) "On the Eigenstructures of Functional K-Potent Matrices and Their Integral Forms" WSEAS Transactions on Mathematics, 9 (1), 244-253.